

Local Government in Moldova

Responses to Urban-Rural Challenges

edited by

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NALAS - Network of Associations of Local Authorities of South East Europe
with the support of the Congress of Local Authorities of Moldova (CALM)

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November 2021

The Country Report on Local Government in Moldova is a product of the LoGov-project: “Local Government and the Changing Urban-Rural Interplay”.

The H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018 project aims to provide solutions for local governments that address the fundamental challenges resulting from urbanisation. To address these complex issues, 18 partners from 17 countries and six continents share their expertise and knowledge in the realms of public law, political science, and public administration. LoGov identifies, evaluates, compares, and shares innovative practices that cope with the impact of changing urban-rural relations in major local government areas (WP 1-5).

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This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 823961.

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Local Financial Arrangements

3.1. Local Financial Arrangements in Moldova: An Introduction

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At first glance Moldova has a highly decentralized public sector with second and first level local authorities responsible for preschools, primary and secondary education, social assistance etc. Local governments in Moldova are responsible for about a fourth of total public revenue, the highest levels in South-East Europe. However, this picture may be misleading. In practice, the central government and its deconcentrated structures continue to hold substantial decision-making powers over local functions and finances. Considering that freely disposable grants and local own revenue together constitute about a fourth of total local revenues, most local governments' functions, besides being severely underfunded, remain de-facto delegated, rather than decentralized.

Given the significant (delegated) responsibilities that Moldovan local governments have to carry out, the budgetary system in Moldova is dominated by intergovernmental transfers. The current framework for own local government revenue mobilization remains largely ineffective because it provides little incentives to local governments for improving revenue collection. The educational sector receives the lion's share of the intergovernmental transfers (77 per cent). Other local government functions, although quite expensive, like the collection and management of household waste, including sanitation and maintenance of land for their storage, or, water supply, construction and maintenance of sewage and wastewater treatment systems, do not get any significant financial support from the state budget.

Shared tax revenues are allocated directly to local governments based on the residence of the employer, in different proportions: 100 per cent for villages, cities (excepting capital cities of *rayons*) and municipalities (excepting Chisinau and Balti); 50 per cent for the capital of Moldova - Chisinau municipality, Balti municipality and cities and municipalities that are also capital cities of a *rayons*; 25 per cent for *rayons*.

The remaining part of the shared tax revenues is withheld and transferred to the Balancing Fund,⁶ which is the source of the General-Purpose Transfer received by local governments. Both, cities and villages (Local Public Administration level 1 [LPA1]) and municipalities (excepting Chisinau and Balti municipalities) and *rayons* (Local Public Administration level 2

⁶ A recent legislative initiative approved by Parliament presumes the allocation of additional resources for the Balancing Fund, through a share of revenues generated by the income tax. However, the precise share of the revenues generated by the income tax that are directed into Balancing Fund will have to be determined by the annual state budget law as it is not prescribed by the law on local finances, leading to even more confusion in the local budgets' formation.

[LPA2]) can benefit from general purpose transfers, which are allocated from the balancing fund, 45 per cent in favor of LPA1 and 55 per cent in favor of LPA2. General purpose transfers are distributed to local governments on the basis of fiscal capacity per inhabitant data, multiplied by a coefficient of 1.3 and then on the basis of the population and size of territory of each LPA1. Fiscal capacity per inhabitant is determined by taking into consideration incomes generated only by the wage tax, regardless of the type of the locality (rural, urban). For LPA2, the allocation criteria refer to population and territory (except for the municipalities of Chisinau and Balti that cannot benefit from general purpose transfers). General purpose transfers are limited to the total amount of the balancing fund. Rules for the general-purpose transfers' distribution do not take into consideration the total amount needed in order to meet the average fiscal capacity per inhabitant for all local public authorities (LPAs) which can lead to a situation when available funds are lower than needed.

The third, and larger, type of intergovernmental transfer is the Special Purpose Conditional Transfer, financed directly from the central government budget. These transfers are allocated to local governments to fund expenditure needs of the educational sector, road infrastructure, delegated functions and capital investment. These transfers do not finance *rayon* or local level social protection services provided by municipalities and *rayons*. Additionally, LPA1, have no competences in the distribution of the funds allocated for the development of the road infrastructure, which limits local financial decentralization.

References to Scientific and Non-Scientific Publications

Law 397/2003 on Local Public Finances

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This project has received funding from
the European Union's Horizon 2020 re-
search and innovation programme under
grant agreement No 823961.

